

THE FEATURE OF RENAISSANCE DRAMATURGY OF THE ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Abstract. This article discusses the features of renaissance dramaturgy of English literature. During the Renaissance in England, dramatic literature, closely connected with the widespread development of theatrical performances and performing arts at that time, reached a special flourishing. Renaissance theater developed in England somewhat differently than in other European countries. Its evolution from medieval theater was much more gradual and organic here than, for example, in Italy or France. Having experienced the influence of both ancient and classical-humanistic dramaturgy of Europe, English drama nevertheless largely retained its folk character, growing directly from the dramatic genres of the Middle Ages - morality plays and interludes.

Keywords: Renaissance, development, drama, humanism, image, genre system, transformation.

English drama of the Renaissance was a synthesis of advanced humanistic ideas and folk drama. Using classical examples of ancient drama, humanists deepened the content and improved the forms of dramatic art. In the mid-16th century, morality plays and interludes were gradually replaced by comedies and tragedies. The first English comedy is considered to be the play by Nicholas Udall, *Ralph Royster Doyster*, 1551, the main character of which represents the English version of the "boastful warrior" Plautus. If the sphere of comedy from the very beginning becomes private life, then in tragedy, starting from its first example, socio-political themes are established.

The play "Gorboduc, or Ferrex and Porrex" is usually considered the first English tragedy. Its authors were lawyers Thomas Sackville and Thomas Norton. King Gorboduc divided his land between his sons Ferrex and Porrex, who plunge the country into internecine war. The whole play is imbued with the idea of the need for the unity of the state. "Gorboduc" uses the model of Seneca's tragedy: a structure in 5 acts, a historical or pseudo-historical theme, an idea fixing the violation of order in the state, an appeal to pantomime, a mixture of rhymed and unrhymed verses.

In 1558, that brilliant period of heyday of English drama of the Renaissance began, the pinnacle of which was the work of Shakespeare. The stage for Shakespeare was prepared by a galaxy of humanist playwrights, nicknamed "the University Wits", since they all had degrees from Cambridge or Oxford. They reign unchallenged for ten years. We are talking about Robert Greene, Christopher Marlowe, Thomas Nashe, John Lyly, George Peel and Thomas Lodge.

The eldest of the "university minds," John Lily, focused his work on courtly and aristocratic circles. His *Euphes* (1580) is an educational novel that paints the image of an ideal gentleman. The style of the novel, later called "Eufuistic," is refined, even pretentious. It is characterized by an abundance of metaphors and comparisons, antitheses, quotes and references to ancient authors. Eufuism had a significant influence on the literary language of the era. Lily is the

creator of "high" comedy in English drama. He introduced complex intrigue into the comedy, as well as new aristocratic issues. Lily's innovation was that he wrote his comedies in prose.

Robert Greene was not only the author of dramas, but also of poems, novels, and pamphlets. Green is the prototype of a professional writer. He lives completely off his pen, even if he lives poorly. Leading a promiscuous bohemian life, Greene dives into London's underbelly and describes the various methods used by unscrupulous people to pinch the naive. The novel "Pandosto: the triumph of time" was written in a different romantic vein. 20 years later he would serve as Shakespeare's source for his *The Winter's Tale*.

It is worth paying attention to Christopher Marlowe (1564-1593). It is he who is credited with the fact that in his plays, which were a resounding success, he outlined features and forms that would become typical for all Elizabethan drama: the choice of unrhymed iambic pentathlon (blank verse), a mixture of verse and prose. Killed in a tavern brawl at the age of 29, Marlowe had an extremely short career. Nevertheless, he left a very significant literary legacy. Marlowe's most popular plays are the tragedies "Tamerlane the Great", "The Jew of Malta", "The Tragic History of Doctor Faustus". In them the author created images of strong titanic heroes. Tamerlane is a man of enormous ambition, an unquenchable thirst for power, indomitable energy and cruelty. Faust strives for unlimited knowledge, which should give him wealth and power over the world. The Maltese Jew, the moneylender Barrabas, embodies the unbridled spirit of acquisitiveness; obsessed with a manic passion for enrichment, he stops at nothing. In Marlowe's work, the concept of the tragic was more deeply developed. Before Marlowe, the tragic was understood externally, as an image of all kinds of atrocities that cause fear and horror. Marlowe himself took this position, creating "Tamerlane" and "The Jew of Malta." "Faust" surpasses both of these dramas in that here the tragic is expressed not so much in the external, but in the internal conflict in the soul of the hero, who sold his soul to the devil in order to satisfy his thirst for power. The tragedy of the monarch reaches the size of a person's personal tragedy in Marlowe's best play, *Edward 2*.

English literature of the Renaissance made the greatest breakthrough in drama, where, of course, the British were ahead of the whole of Europe. English theater reached its highest development in the 1580s–1590s. Initially, English drama was associated with the imitation of ancient drama, and plays were written based on plots from ancient history. By 1580, English drama was already characterized by a special variety of genres and produced a number of brilliant playwrights. John Lyly's plays, full of lush rhetoric, were addressed to the court audience, but in them, like Robert Greene, one can notice a clearly expressed patriotic orientation and closeness to folk tales (*The Comedy of George Greene, the Weckfield Field Watchman*). Since the time of Thomas Kyd's *Spanish Tragedy*, "bloody drama" has come into use. In general, drama was characterized by a variety of genres (tragedy, comedy, historical play, even pastoral) and playwrights were unusually prolific (which was explained by the needs of the stage and the audience). The specificity of English dramaturgy was also the continuing mixture of high and low genres in one play, which provided the effect of contrast and subsequently deeply outraged the theorists of classicism.

The peculiarity of this theater was that, relying on the national past, the ancient heritage and the achievements of the Renaissance culture, it was able, in a language accessible to the widest masses, using grandiose images, to raise the eternal questions of human existence, the meaning of his life, purpose, time and eternity, the relationship individuals and society.

Playwrights who had actors at hand (they usually worked with the troupe and wrote based on its capabilities) not only brought titanic characters to the stage, but also raised the question of the moral responsibility of the individual to society, about what the unlimited freedom of the extraordinary brings with it. A person for other, albeit not so great, people, what is the fate of the people in "fatal moments." At the turn of the 16th–17th centuries, the theater was able to summarize all the experience accumulated by the Renaissance and express it, deepening the ideas put forward earlier. The work of the first great tragic playwright, Christopher Marlowe (1564–1593), expressed these doubts and contradictions. Marlowe created the image of Faust, who sought to reorganize the world. Through the lips of another of his characters, the cruel conqueror, the illiterate shepherd Tamerlane, the playwright sets out his understanding of the destiny of man; the "anxious and indomitable spirit" draws him to action and knowledge. Marlowe's heroes for the first time showed the other side of the ideal of the Renaissance man - they are extraordinary and oppose society, violating not only its laws, but also generally accepted norms of humanity. Because of their immorality, they evoked both horror and admiration. With the work of Marlowe, a new stage in the development of dramaturgy of the English Renaissance begins, which turned out to be associated with the analysis of internal spiritual contradictions, with the image of a grandiose personality inevitably drawn to death. The pinnacle of the development of the Renaissance (and European theater) is the work of William Shakespeare (1564–1616). The exact number of his plays and the time of their creation are unknown; based on an analysis of the first posthumous edition, researchers identified 37 plays (the so-called canon) and proposed dates. Recently, some researchers have tended to add to him certain works traditionally attributed to Shakespeare, and the debate about the authorship of the entire heritage has again resumed. Creativity is divided into three periods. The first period (1590–1600) consists mainly of comedies; most of them are lyrical, some are everyday, others include elements of a romantic fairy tale or pastoral. All of them expressed the ideals of the Renaissance, are imbued with the joy of life, glorify human feelings and human activity, deeply humanistic (A Midsummer Night's Dream, Much Ado About Nothing, Twelfth Night, The Merry Wives of Windsor). His first tragedies on subjects from ancient history (Julius Caesar) also date back to the same period, and a cycle of historical plays dedicated to national history (chronicles) was created, in which the historical and political concept of the playwright was expressed (Richard II, Henry IV, Henry V, Richard III, etc.). It was in them that he first examined the problem of power, ruler, tyranny, the role of the people in the political life of the country and the legitimacy of power. At the turn of the first and second periods, the most poetic of Shakespeare's tragedies was created - a true hymn to love dying due to the inertia of society (Romeo and Juliet). The second period (1601–1602) was characterized by a crisis of the humanistic worldview and the playwright's turn to the genre of tragedy. The tragedies had the deepest philosophical content. In them, the Renaissance hero confronts not only a hostile world, but also a new time, the Renaissance harmony of the individual and society is destroyed. It was in tragedies (Hamlet, King Lear, Macbeth, the Roman tragedies Antony and Cleopatra and Coriolanus) that Shakespeare showed the most complex psychological struggle and dialectic of passions in the souls of his characters, revealing the depth of the conflict. The third period (1608–1612) was characterized by the appearance of romantic, almost fairy-tale plays (Cymbeline, The Winter's Tale, especially The Tempest), permeated with nostalgia for the ideals of the Renaissance, Shakespeare remained faithful to the ideals of the Renaissance - a

harmoniously developed person is the “crown of all things”, but he is given the power to decide the fate of the world only outside the familiar world, in a fairy tale (utopia, pastoral).

Shakespeare in his work so deeply revealed the contradictions of human nature and comprehended the fate of the individual and society that he not only deepened the ideas of Renaissance humanism, but his understanding of man, thoughts and experiences were perceived by later eras, and the plays entered the golden fund of eternal works, and without them To this day, the activity of a drama theater is unthinkable. The name of Shakespeare is associated with the concept of “tragic humanism”: awareness of the tragedy of an individual forced to enter into a struggle with society. Almost always this struggle is doomed, but necessary and inevitable. Shakespeare fully shared the ideals of the Renaissance, but the central conflict of his plays was determined by the discrepancy between the Renaissance ideal of man and reality. Society is hostile to this ideal.

A critical attitude towards an imperfect society is associated with its attitude towards time, a powerful force, which, however, does not correspond to the principles of the world order, in the figurative expression of the playwright: “Time has dislocated the joint.” This dooms most of Shakespeare's heroes to inevitable death, and even in comedies with happy endings, the heroes go through severe trials. Most of his heroes strive to comprehend not only themselves, but also their time, and the place of man in the world and eternity, and the confrontation between good and evil. Reflection, their understanding of their purpose, fate, and mistakes lead them to enlightenment.

The greatness of Shakespeare lies in the fact that he was able to raise questions that concern people at all times, make the ideals of the Renaissance close to posterity and create unusually complex, versatile, psychologically deep images. Shakespeare inherited the ideal of man from the Renaissance, but the note of bitterness already anticipates a different time. Shakespeare's successors (the “younger Elizabethans”) already expressed not only the crisis of Renaissance ideals, but also the tragic perception of the world characteristic of Mannerism and Baroque.

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